

Monocular Visual Odometry for Assistive Lower Limb Exoskeletons

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Abstract—Assistive Lower Limb Exoskeletons (LLEs) offer significant potential for individuals with impaired lower limb mobility. However, current LLEs are limited by their reliance on predefined movements that do not account for the surrounding environment. In our previous solution [1] we employed an RGB-D camera to develop an environment-adaptive gait planning system that only considered the latest detection to reason upon the environment, which is unsuitable in many scenarios. In this work, we aim to upgrade our environment understanding system by employing deep learning methods for monocular visual odometry (VO): in this way, the environment can be mapped, greatly expanding gait planning capabilities, while also lowering the camera requirements.

Index Terms—lower-limb exoskeletons, visual odometry, mapping

I. INTRODUCTION

Assistive lower-limb exoskeletons (LLEs) are wearable robotic devices aimed at helping people with lower limb impairments regain mobility [2]. While some exoskeletons are commercially available [3], their use is primarily restricted to clinical or research environments [4]. This is mainly because most commercial LLEs depend on pre-programmed walking patterns, or at best, are tailored for individual users [5], making them unsuitable for varied everyday settings. Current solutions provide predefined modes for different terrains [2] but often require manual switching [6] and do not adapt in real-time to environmental obstacles. Although we already proposed and validated a solution for obstacle avoidance [7], such solution would only process the current state of the environment, captured through the means of a RGB-D camera; this approach poses many problems, since obstacles outside the Field of View (FOV) of the camera will be neglected, exposing the user to risk of collisions. Moreover, the narrow range of single-scan camera data would limit the gait planning horizon. To overcome these limitations, we aim to enhance our framework

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with Deep Learning methods for Monocular Visual Odometry (VO): in such a way, we could greatly expand the planning horizon by considering obstacles out of the camera FOV, while also lowering the camera requirements at the time of deployment (from RGB-D to RGB).

II. MATERIALS & METHODS

A. Dataset

Fig. 1. A schematic representation of the dataset collection setup.

We aim to create a dataset of indoor scenes suitable, in particular, to train and evaluate methods for monocular VO in the field of assistive lower limb exoskeletons. The data required by these systems is peculiar due to the viewpoint required for the cameras or any other visual sensors. Deep learning methods for monocular VO [8] necessitate large amount of data to train. Most monocular (and also stereo) VO public datasets are collected in outdoor [9] or indoor [10] environments, but none, to the best of our knowledge, is collected from a lower limb point of view, facing downward

and frontally from a walking person perspective. Thus, we want to create a dataset to answer the need for a lower limb monocular point of view. As can be seen in Fig. 1, the setup for the dataset collection that we propose is composed of two synchronized RGB-D cameras, e.g., Intel® RealSense™ Depth Camera D435i, comprising of an inertial measurement unit (IMU), mounted on a rigid structure. We assume to know the extrinsic \mathbf{T}_e between the two cameras and the intrinsic calibration parameters. The rigid structure can be worn by a person so that the RGB camera always faces upward, while the RGB-D camera always faces downward and frontally, framing the scene that might be affected by a new step. To scan a scene, we prepare it before the data collection by distributing apriltags on the ceiling of the room, for which we know exactly the pose of each apriltag in the ceiling 2D plane. In this way, the camera facing upward always frames at least one apriltag, allowing for the computation of the relative transformation \mathbf{T}_i of the upward facing camera with respect to the i -th apriltag by using a pose estimation algorithm. We also scan the scene with a LiDAR sensor, in order to create a high-precision 3D point cloud map of the scene. To do so, we post-process all the collected LiDAR scans by using a point cloud registration algorithm. The ground truth annotation of our monocular VO dataset is obtained by integrating the IMU readings (filtered with a Kalman filter) and the apriltag-based pose estimations \mathbf{T}_i . We can then produce pairs of RGB-D images and 6 DoF poses with respect to the initial frame of reference.

B. Mapping

We propose a method for indoor monocular VO based on D3VO [8], a self-supervised monocular VO framework that predicts the depth from a single RGB image and the pose between two adjacent frames. To deal with the inconsistent illumination between the image pairs, the network predicts the brightness transformation parameters which align the brightness of source and target images during training. D3VO is trained using videos of stereo image pairs by minimizing the minimum of the photometric re-projection errors between the temporal (I_{t-1}, I_{t+1}) and static stereo images (I_t^s) . We want to adapt the training pipeline to adapt it to our dataset and improve the performance. First, we don't have stereo images pairs, but we have the real depth channel \mathbf{D} of each image. As in D3VO, our network takes 2 channel-wise concatenated images (e.g., I_{t-1} concatenated with I_t or I_t concatenated with I_{t+1}). We can train our system to infer the depth $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_{t-1}$ of the previous RGB image I_{t-1} and the depth $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_{t+1}$ of the subsequent RGB image I_{t+1} using the real depths \mathbf{D}_{t-1} and \mathbf{D}_{t+1} . We compute the loss terms $\mathcal{L}_{\text{dep}}^{t-1}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{dep}}^{t+1}$. We claim that training for depth estimation will help to learn useful weights for subsequent tasks, such as relative pose estimation.

We can train the network to predict the relative transformation $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{t-1}^t$ between I_{t-1} and I_t , or $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_t^{t+1}$ between I_t and I_{t+1} by using the ground truth annotation of our dataset and computing the loss terms $\mathcal{L}_{\text{pos}}^{t-1}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{pos}}^{t+1}$.

As a new source of information, we can add a loss term by comparing the point cloud obtained by using the depth

estimation by the system and the real point cloud map of the scene obtained with the LiDAR sensor, and computing the photometric re-projection error $\mathcal{L}_{\text{map}}^{t-1}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{map}}^{t+1}$.

Finally, the total loss function is given by:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{tot}} = (\mathcal{L}_{\text{dep}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{pos}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{map}})^{t-1} + (\mathcal{L}_{\text{dep}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{pos}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{map}})^{t+1} \quad (1)$$

We regard that the combination of these information sources can lead to an improved performance of the system and can allow it to produce a reliable monocular VO for assistive lower limb exoskeletons.

III. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have presented a novel framework aimed at enhancing the obstacle avoidance capabilities of assistive LLEs through the integration of deep learning-based monocular VO. Through a dataset of indoor scenes captured from a lower limb perspective, we aim to adapt the D3VO architecture to effectively handle the specific use-case of LLEs. Finally, we plan to deploy this system in real-world scenarios to validate its performance, with a particular focus on improving the exoskeleton's adaptability to complex indoor environments and obstacles outside the immediate field of view.

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